

Teachers' Perceptions of the Impact of the Grinds Culture: A Focus on Post-Primary Mathematics

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Grinds can be defined as education outside the formal schooling system where a tutor teaches a particular subject(s) in exchange for a financial gain. Their provision has become a widespread phenomenon internationally in recent years, no more so than for the subject of mathematics. In this paper we sought to investigate mathematics teachers' perceptions of the impact of the grinds culture in the subject at post-primary level in Ireland. The data was gathered using an online survey designed by the authors and circulated to post-primary mathematics teachers in November 2020. The findings from responding teachers (n = 305) revealed mixed opinions, with both positive and negative impacts identified. Many teachers acknowledged the benefits of one-to-one support that grinds can provide and the resulting increase in students' confidence in the subject. However, teachers also noted that for some students', grinds can be a substitute for a lack of motivation and work ethic and their provision can often lead to disengagement in class.

Introduction

In this paper we sought to investigate mathematics teachers' perceptions of the impact of the grinds culture in the subject at post-primary level in Ireland. Grinds, often referred to as 'shadow education', are defined by Smyth (2009, p.2) as "*paid private tuition outside of, and additional to, the formal schooling system*". In essence, they involve additional tutoring outside of the formal school day. Stevenson and Baker (1992) termed it 'shadow education' as all members of the tutoring triangle (tutors, students and parents) wish for it to remain low profile. Yung and Bray (2017) also noted that it 'shadows' and to some extent copies the regular school curriculum. For many decades shadow education has been popular in East Asian countries influenced by Confucian cultural traditions including China, South Korea, Hong Kong, and Japan (Bray, 2013). For example, in China the 2004 'Urban Household Education and Employment' survey indicated that tutoring was received by 74% of primary, 66% of lower secondary and 54% of upper secondary students (Bray, 2009). However, in recent years there has been a notable surge in the uptake of private tuition globally with Bray (2020) reporting that this phenomenon is now prevalent across the globe. With regard to Ireland, Smyth (2009) reported that 45% of students surveyed in her sample had received grinds in their final year of schooling in 2003. This was a significant increase from 32% of the same age-group a decade earlier (Smyth, 2009). More recently, using data from the 'Growing up in Ireland' study, McCoy and Byrne (2019) reported that 60% of Irish 17 years olds participated in 'shadow education'.

Due to the prevalence of private tuition, many researchers have sought to ascertain the factors which drive the uptake of grinds. In Ireland, the Leaving Certificate (LC) examination acts as a gatekeeper to third-level education as a student's entry relies almost entirely on their

performance in this summative State examination. A study carried out by Smyth and Banks (2012, p. 302) determined that students' performance in the LC has 'very significant consequences for young people's future life chances'. There is no doubting that high stakes nature of such terminal examinations are a driving force in the uptake of grinds. This is not just an Irish occurrence. For example, similar findings were reported in many districts of China where examinations in upper and lower secondary school have become increasingly competitive and has led to parents enrolling their children in private tuition in order to enhance their chances of being accepted into prestigious schools or universities (Zhang & Bray, 2016). Interestingly, the Finnish education system does not place an emphasis on high stakes examinations, and this is one of the few countries where shadow education is "barely visible" (Bray, 2020, p.4).

While the provision of grinds can be found across almost every subject, a UK study by Ireson and Rushforth (2005) found that mathematics was the subject area where private tuition was most in demand. They found that 19% of students in Year 13 (students aged 17-18 years old) reported receiving private tuition in mathematics while only 8% of students received private tuition in the next most popular subject, English. Their study also found that less than 3% of students were availing of private tuition across other curricular subjects. More recently, these findings were supported by the work of Kim and Jung-Hoon (2019) and that of Bray (2013, p. 415) who found that "Mathematics and the national languages tend to be in especially high demand [for private tuition]". In Ireland, Smyth et al. (2007) found that a significantly higher proportion of students availed of mathematics grinds compared to other subjects.

There are many interlinking reasons why the demand for mathematics grinds may be high, compared to other subjects. Bray (2020) asserted that many avail of additional tutoring in order to compensate for shortcomings in the mainstream education system. In Ireland, Prendergast and O'Meara (2017) reported on shortcomings in relation to an overcrowded mathematics curriculum and a shortage of class time to complete this curriculum. Furthermore, as previously mentioned, the LC examination, acts as a gatekeeper to third-level education in Ireland. However, its high stakes nature is even more pronounced for the subject of mathematics. Firstly, the subject is considered a necessary entry requirement for many college courses. Secondly, since 2012, students are now awarded an extra 25 'bonus points' in their overall LC examination results if they achieve $\geq 40\%$ in advanced mathematics. This initiative has resulted in record numbers now opting for the Higher Level (HL) paper at both Junior and Senior Cycle. For example, between the years 2011 – 2019 the numbers taking LC HL mathematics have increased from 15.8% to 32.9% (SEC, 2011 - 2019). While there are many merits in increasing the numbers studying mathematics at an advanced level, there have been some unwarranted consequences. For example, in a study by Prendergast, O'Meara, and Treacy (2020), many responding teachers voiced concerns about the mathematical standard of some students now continuing at HL. Some believed that the awarding of bonus points are promoting a 'grinds culture' in the subject; 'It promotes a grinds culture where if a parent throws enough money at the problem the problem will be solved...' (Teacher response in Prendergast et al., 2020). The research detailed in this paper aimed to explore mathematics teachers' perceptions

of the impact of this ‘grinds culture’ in more detail. It sought to address the following research question:

- What are mathematics teachers’ perceptions of the impact of the grinds culture at post-primary level in Ireland?

Methodology

As part of a larger study, the authors designed an online survey that sought to investigate mathematics teachers’ perceptions of the scale, nature, driving forces, and impact of the grinds culture that currently exists in the subject at post-primary level in Ireland. Given that almost all of the studies on grinds have been conducted quantitatively (Hajar, 2018), the survey the authors designed enabled them to generate mixed data through the inclusion of dichotomous, multiple choice, Likert scales and open-ended questions. The finalised instrument, which was piloted with eight experienced mathematics teachers, comprised of six sections. One of these sections focused specifically on the impact of grinds. Here teachers were asked to indicate their level of agreement with a series of seven statements on the impact of grinds on various domains using a five-point Likert scale. Four of these statements related directly to the impact of grinds on students’ knowledge, understanding, and performance in mathematics. For example, ‘In general, receiving grinds increases students’ conceptual understanding of mathematical concepts’. The remaining three statements were associated with the impact of grinds on the affective domain in the subject. For example, ‘In general, receiving grinds improves students’ attitudes towards mathematics’. These Likert scale statements were preceded by an open-ended question where teachers were asked for further comment on their opinion regarding the impact of grinds.

The target sample for this study was all teachers of mathematics across the 723 post-primary schools in Ireland. The Qualtrics survey was distributed online, and the link was widely circulated on a variety of social media platforms and to a number of professional bodies, including the Irish Mathematics Teacher Association. In total, 305 teachers responded to the survey.

The quantitative data for this paper, which provided information on teachers’ level of agreement on the impact of grinds on various domains, was recorded in SPSS and was analysed using descriptive statistics. The data from the subsequent open-ended question on impact was transcribed into a Microsoft Word document and an inductive ‘bottom up’ thematic content analysis was performed on the teachers’ responses in relation to the positive and negative impacts of the grinds culture. The work of Braun and Clarke (2006) provided a framework for this analysis. It was a flexible and recursive process, with repeated movement back and forth as initial codes were generated, and themes were reviewed.

Findings

As noted, 305 mathematics teachers responded to the survey and 38% of these identified as currently giving grinds. The data in relation to teachers’ levels of agreement ($n = 284$) with each of the seven statements are outlined in Figures 1 and 2. As evidenced from

Figure 1, 76% of responding teachers were in agreement that receiving grinds increases students’ performance in mathematical assessments. However, less than half of this number (36%), agreed that receiving grinds increases students' problem-solving capabilities.

Figure 1

Teachers’ levels of agreement as to the impact on grinds on improving various domains

Regarding the affective domain, the highest proportion of teachers (82%) were in agreement that receiving grinds increases students’ confidence in mathematics. However, on the other hand, only 35% agreed that receiving grinds positively alters students' behaviour in the classroom.

Figure 2

Teachers’ levels of agreement as to the impact on grinds on improving the affective domain

These findings were elaborated on through the open-ended question where teachers were asked for further comment on their opinion regarding the impact of grinds. Analysis of this data highlights the mixed views of teachers with both positive and negative impacts being noted.

From a positive perspective, the most common impact that teachers noted was the benefit of one-to-one support that grinds can provide for struggling students.

T114: Weaker students sometimes just need the one-to-one element to help them grasp a concept.

T212: One-on-one will always be a more effective way of communicating an idea to a student.

In line with the quantitative data, many teachers also mentioned increased student confidence as a positive impact.

T175: Some students need that reinforcement and it gives them the confidence to excel in the subject.

T220: I believe they can be highly effective in instilling confidence in a student.

Other positive impacts noted by some teachers were that grinds are an opportunity for students to ask questions and seek help (T84: Opportunity to ask the questions that they won't ask in class) and also that they can increase student understanding and improve grades.

From a negative perspective, there were a number of common impacts that responding teachers noted. The first was that grinds often lead to disengagement in class.

T8: Students often participate less in class, they won't ask questions as they feel like it's okay as they will do it in their grinds.

T157: Students become disengaged in the classroom because when they encounter something difficult they don't need to try and I quote ..." I'll do it in grinds"....

Secondly, it was noted that grinds are often a substitute for lack of student motivation and work ethic.

T20: Papering over the cracks of a culture of minimal effort.

T134: Many students think doing a grind a week is a substitute for hard work and study.

Following on from this, some teachers felt that grinds encourage rote learning and are exam focused.

T298: Students will frequently be shown shortcuts and tricks. Focus is very often on the answer rather than the process.

Furthermore, they can lead to students developing a negative attitude/ opinion towards the class teacher.

T94: Often it can alter a students opinion of the teacher negatively. They often think their grinds teacher is 'better' than their teacher. Maybe sometimes that is true. However, there is a huge difference in one-on-one help and sitting in a class with 30 other students which they don't consider.

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal the mixed views that mathematics teachers have in relation to the impact of the grinds culture that is permeating the subject at post-primary level in Ireland. There is no doubting the benefits of the one-to-one support that grinds can provide. As summed up by one responding teacher, ‘there is a huge difference in one-on-one help and sitting in a class with 30 other students’. This positive impact of grinds was also noted by students in a UK study conducted by Hajar (2018). One student noted that “instead of the teacher talking to everyone they’re just talking to you and giving you advice on what you should do in a specific task” (p. 523). This is best summed up by Kim (2016) who noted that grinds can focus on the needs, learning styles and academic goals of the individual student. Such personalised attention can undoubtedly have a positive impact on students’ affective domain (Hajar, 2018). Responding teachers in this study were very cognisant of this positive impact, particularly in relation to students’ confidence. For example, of all seven Likert scale statements, the highest proportion of teachers (82%) were in agreement that receiving grinds increases students’ confidence in the subject. Given the well documented issues around the affective domain in mathematics, which are often associated with low confidence, low self-concept, and mathematics anxiety, particularly in relation to female students (O’Rourke & Prendergast, 2021) and students attending DEIS schools (Perkins et al., 2013), this is an important positive impact. However, not every family can pay for grinds and thus these potential positive impacts are not available to all and can exacerbate rather than improve social inequalities (Bray & Kwok, 2003). As one responding teacher in this study noted “You pay and you get the privilege and advantage that puts you up the pecking order”.

While these impacts of grinds on creating further inequality and also covering up wider systemic issues (e.g. shortage of class time and overcrowded curriculum) were mentioned by some teachers, the main negative impacts that emerged were more classroom related. Although 76% of responding teachers were in agreement that receiving grinds increases students’ performance in mathematical assessments, it was clear from the qualitative data that teachers felt that grinds are often a substitute for a lack of student motivation and work ethic in class. This is in line with some of the criticisms noted by teachers in a study by Wang and Bray (2016) investigating attitudes towards private supplementary tutoring in Hong Kong. One teacher in their study noted that “It also gives students a wrong perception that they don’t have to work hard. They can just rely on tutoring” (p.879). In a related point, a strong theme to emerge from the qualitative data of this study was that grinds often lead to disengagement in class. In the quantitative data, one in four teachers also disagreed that receiving grinds improves students’ classroom behaviour. A similar finding was noted in the work of Zhan et al. (2013) who determined that private tutoring may have reduced the students’ respect for their teachers.

Given the dearth of research in this area, particularly from an Irish perspective, this paper offers important insights into Irish mathematics teachers perceptions of the grinds culture. There is no doubt that shadow education can be helpful and have positive effects on student learning and society (Kim & Jung-Hoon, 2019). On the other hand, it also has potential for distorting some educational processes and may have social repercussions such as greater

inequalities (Baker, 2020). Despite this, there is an air of inevitability to its continued growth. As determined by Byun and Baker (2015), the provision of grinds is ‘unlikely to be banned or fall into disuse as its connection to the main social institution of formal education has become too strong’ (p.10). Thus, it is important that research such as this continues to investigate the impact of grinds from a variety of perspectives and hypothesize how it may shape the future of education.

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